

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D6.8 Report on 5G PPP collaboration activities

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Contributors and Peer Reviewers

Contributors
Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Vangelis Kosmatos (WINGS), Giada Landi (NXW), Juan Brenes (NXW), Ronan Frizzell (ICP), Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), Cornelia Alexandru, Lucian Necula, Ion Marghescu (BEIA), Silviu Ciochina (BEIA), Gabriel Petrescu (BEIA), Alexandru Vulpe (BEIA), George Suciu (BEIA), Razvan Bratulescu (BEIA), Andreea Bonea (ORO), Marius Iordache (ORO), Alexandru Oprea (ORO)
Peer Reviewers
Ronan Frizzell (ICP), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	6G Industry Association
API	Application Programming Interface
BVME	Business Validation, Models, and Ecosystems
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CI / CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CMC	Connected Motorcycle Consortium
E2E	End to End
EC	European Commission
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
IA	Innovation Action
ICT	Information & Communication Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union – Telecommunication Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine learning

Abbreviation / Term	Description
NetApp	Network Application
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
PC	Project Coordinator
R&I	Research and Innovation
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RRU	Remote Radio Unit
SB	Steering Board
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
SNS	Smart Networks & Services
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
T&L	Transport & logistics
TB	Technology Board
TM	Technical Manager
TMV	Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation
TR	Technical Report
UC	Use Case

VIM	Virtual Infrastructure manager
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VSF	Vertical Service Blueprint

WG	Work Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the overview of VITAL-5G's participation in the various bodies and activities of 5G Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) and the details regarding the contributions and outcomes of VITAL-5G's partners in the respective Working Groups (WGs), during the first reporting period of the project, namely M1-M18 (January 2021 – June 2022). As part of its activities, the VITAL-5G project actively participates and contributes to multiple 5G PPP bodies, in order to i) engage in discussion and exchange knowledge and lessons learned with other EU funded projects working on similar subjects, ii) disseminate its results/outcomes to groups of relevant experts and receive feedback, iii) align and adjust its goals and work according to relevant findings from other projects which affect the work of VITAL-5G and iv) to contribute to the generation of relevant knowledge and the broad dissemination of EU funded R&I programs through the active contributions in White Papers.

The project partners have identified the most relevant 5G PPP bodies and actively participate in their activities. The engagement of VITAL-5G with the various 5G PPP bodies and activities, for the first reporting period (M1-M18) can be summarized as follows:

- Constant participation in the 5G PPP Steering Board (SB) & Technology Board (TB)
- Participation in eight (8) relevant WGs
- Active contribution to all the 5G PPP documentation
- Contributions to seven (7) White papers
- Co-organization of two (2) 5G PPP Workshops/Special Sessions
- Collaboration with two (2) initiatives

As the project matures and proceeds to the trial and results generation phase (2nd reporting period M19-M36), the volume of concrete output towards the 5G PPP bodies is expected to increase, which will be reflected by the number of specific contributions to the 5G PPP during the 2nd reporting period.

1 Introduction

The VITAL-5G project operates within the context of the Horizon 2020 framework and under the umbrella of the 5G Public Private Partnership (5G PPP¹), alongside projects addressing the same Research and Innovation (R&I) call (ICT-41-2020) as well as projects addressing different calls but engaging with relevant technologies and common targets. The VITAL-5G partners fully understand that they don't operate in an isolated environment, but are rather part of a complex ecosystem, which requires the exchange of knowledge and insights among projects and experts in order to capitalize on the project results and to maximize the research and socio-economic impact of the project outcomes. In this context, the VITAL-5G project has adopted a coordinated approach towards the participation of its partners and the representation of the project within 5G PPP, participating not only in the Steering Board (SB) and Technology Board (TB) groups (which is considered pretty much mandatory) but also to all other 5G PPP Working Groups (WGs) that are relevant to the project's objectives and the technologies used.

In this deliverable, the coordinated approach of VITAL-5G towards participation in 5G PPP activities and contributions to the various WGs is presented, including the exact partners responsible for representing the project in the various WGs. An overview of the VITAL-5G partners activities for the first 18 months of the project (M1-M18) and their contributions to the various WGs is also given, on a per WG basis, while an overview of the most important outcomes of the collaboration of VITAL-5G with other projects, in the context of 5G PPP, is presented in the final Section.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. Table 1 provides this matching for VITAL-5G.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Section 1.3.3 Liaisons with 5G PPP, relevant projects and transferable assets	VITAL-5G builds on the outputs and findings of completed and ongoing 5G PPP projects as well as other relevant projects and commercial assets to seed its technology in support of a significant 5G enablement for the T&L sectoral actors. The VITAL-5G partners will act as liaisons between VITAL-5G and these projects to ensure a smooth flow of information among the projects, the successful integration of relevant outputs from other projects and the further development / enhancements of assets	Section 2.4 Section 3	The collaboration of VITAL-5G project partners with other existing projects in the context of 5G PPP WGs is presented in Section 2.4, while the concrete outcomes of these collaborations are presented in Section 3.

¹ <https://5g-ppp.eu/>

Task 6.4 5G PPP collaboration activities	The only way to achieve such a broad impact is to work together with other projects at 5G PPP level with the aim to establish cross-industry 5G standards, onboard and take advantage of virtualization services and define the exploitation plan at 5G PPP level	Section 2.4	The exact contributions to the 5G PPP WGs and participations to activities of 5G PPP are presented in Section 2.4.
Task 6.4 5G PPP collaboration activities	This task will also ensure, proper, on time and insightful input towards the 5G PPP Steering Board (PC), the Technical Board (TM) and the relevant WGs (partners), thus contributing towards the 5G PPP vision and the shaping / service of the CEF2 vision	Section 2.2 Section 2.3	The contributions of the VITAL-5G project to the 5G PPP SB and TB are highlighted in Sections 2.2 and 2.3.
DELIVERABLE			
D6.8. Report on 5G PPP collaboration activities			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is providing concise information about the activities of the VITAL-5G project within the 5G PPP WGs for the first eighteen months of the project’s life. During this reporting period, the project partners actively participated in all relevant discussions regarding requirements gathering and analysis, architecture, orchestration of services and NetApp design. The activities and contributions of each partner to the 5G PPP WGs and the coordination of these actions from the project’s perspective as part of WP6 ongoing work, are presented in this deliverable. The rest of this document is organized as follows:

- Section 2 provides the overview of the VITAL-5G partners participation in the various 5G PPP WGs and the way of coordination of these activities, while a more detailed account of the contributions of VITAL-5G to each of the WGs is also provided.
- Section 3 provides the aggregated overview of the concrete outcomes of VITAL-5G partners’ contributions to whitepaper, workshop and other types of events
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable and discusses the next steps of this activity

2 VITAL-5G Participation in 5G PPP

The 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) is a joint initiative between the European Commission (EC) and European ICT industry (ICT manufacturers, telecommunications operators, service providers, SMEs and researcher Institutions). The key objective of the 5G PPP is to deliver solutions and technologies and to promote their standardization in order to support the next generation communication infrastructures that will support the digitization and advancement of society. To that end, several Research and Innovation Action (RIA) and Innovation Action (IA) projects have been funded under the umbrella of the 5G PPP organisation, each addressing a specific call to action within the Horizon 2020 (H2020) programme of the EC. The H2020² programme was a R&I initiative that run between 2014 and 2020 with a funding of almost 80 billion €. The latest projects that were commissioned around 2020, including VITAL-5G, are still active and participating in all the joint activities of 5G PPP.

5G PPP is governed by the Steering Board (SB) with the mandatory participation of all the Project Coordinators (PC) of the funded projects under the umbrella of 5G PPP, while key technical insights and the technical roadmap to be followed by 5G PPP are offered by the Technology Board (TB) with the mandatory participation of all the Technical Managers (TM) of the funded projects. Within the SB and TB, the project representatives offer updates regarding the progress of their respective projects, their achievements and key outcomes and collaborate with each other to try and put forth a common understanding and relevant insights about key technological issues such as optimal architecture of solutions, KPI and requirements analysis work, security and regulatory issues and many more. Through the combined learning of all the 5G PPP projects and the exchange of knowledge among their participants, the EC and their private counter-part forming the 5G PPP, i.e., the 6G Industry Association³ (6G-IA) form their strategy and R&I agenda for the upcoming research topics.

Besides the SB and TB which set the tone and draw the strategy of 5G PPP, several Working Groups (WGs) have been created, where experts from all the 5G PPP projects can meet and discuss specific technical issues, in an attempt to learn from each other and to offer consolidated, verified information to the world, based on communal learnings. The work of these WGs usually builds up to tangible results such as webinars, workshops and white-papers, via which the participating experts share their findings with the research and industry communities and help shape the next steps of the European R&I programme.

VITAL-5G partners have a strong and active participation in multiple 5G PPP WGs, that are relevant to the project's work, in an effort to further disseminate the outcomes of the project's work and to learn from other similar project insights. The detailed account of VITAL-5G's approach and participation to the 5G PPP activities, is provided in the following sections on a per WG basis.

2.1 Overview of Work Group Participation

The VITAL-5G project complies with the rules of the 5G PPP programme and the Grant Agreement (GA) signed with the EC and has permanent representatives in the 5G PPP SB and TB, the Project Coordinator (PC) and the Technical Manager (TM) respectively. These two representatives are tasked with providing updates and progress reports to the SB and TB respectively, and to align with the representatives of the other projects on important agenda issues. In order to ensure the participation of a VITAL-5G representative in all the SB and TB meetings, deputies have also been nominated for the SB and TB, which can substitute the PC and TM at the SB and TB meetings, in case they have a conflict and cannot attend a specific meeting. This way the VITAL-5G project always keeps up with the developments in the 5G PPP and ensures that all action points are addressed on time.

Besides the participation in the SB and TB activities, at the beginning of the project, the most interesting and relevant groups of 5G PPP from the VITAL-5G's perspective were identified, and project representatives were

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-2020_en#:~:text=Latest-What%20was%20Horizon%202020%3F,the%20archived%20Horizon%202020%20website.

³ <https://6g-ia.eu/>

nominated for each of them, tasked with the representation of the project in the respective WG and the liaison with other projects on relevant issues. The groups that were identified to be relevant with VITAL-5G's scope of work are the ones addressing 5G architectural issues, vertical service issues, SW development and orchestration issues and of course Network Applications (NetApps) issues.

The complete overview of all the WGs that VITAL-5G participates in, the corresponding responsible partner and their contact information, is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: VITAL-5G delegates in the 5G PPP bodies and WGs

5G PPP WG name	VITAL-5G partner participating	Contact person (name)	Contact person (email)
Steering Board (SB)	WINGS	Kostas Trichias	ktrichias@wings-ict-solutions.eu
	ICP	Ronan Frizzell	ronan.frizzell@inlecomsystems.com
Technology Board (TB)	NXW	Giada Landi	g.landi@nextworks.it
	WINGS	Kostas Trichias	ktrichias@wings-ict-solutions.eu
Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation (TMV)	WINGS	Kostas Trichias Vangelis Kosmatos	ktrichias@wings-ict-solutions.eu vkosmatos@wings-ict-solutions.eu
Vision and Societal Challenges WG	ICP	Patrick Durkin, Ronan Frizzell	patrick.durkin@inlecomsystems.com
	BEIA	Alexandru Vulpe	alex.vulpe@beia.ro
Software Network WG	ORO	Marius Iordache	marius.iordache@orange.com
	IMEC	Johann Marquez-Barja	Johann.Marquez-Barja@imec.be
5G Architecture WG	ORO	Marius Iordache	marius.iordache@orange.com
	OTE	Christina Lessi	clessi@oteresearch.gr
5G Security WG	ORO	Ioan Constantin	ioan.constantin@orange.com
	BEIA	George Suciu	george@beia.ro
Trials WG	BEIA	Alexandru Vulpe	alex.vulpe@beia.ro
	EBOS	Andreas Kartakoullis	andreask@ebos.com.cy
5G for Connected and Automated Mobility (5G4CAM) WG	IMEC	Johann Marquez-Barja	Johann.Marquez-Barja@imec.be
	BEIA	George Suciu	george@beia.ro
5G-PPP SME WG	EBOS	Andreas Gavrielides	andreasg@ebos.com.cy
	ICP	Patrick Durkin	patrick.durkin@inlecomsystems.com
	BEIA	George Suciu	george@beia.ro

The participation of the VITAL-5G partners in the above mentioned WGs takes place in a coordinated manner to maximize the benefits from the project's participation in the 5G PPP activities. The target is to make sure that all of the project's outcomes are properly disseminated to the right channels and reach fellow experts from other projects, while also ensuring that all relevant activities taking place in other projects within 5G PPP are well known to the project partners, to achieve learnings transfer and avoid duplication of work.

This process is coordinated through Work Package 6 (WP6) and more specifically from Task T6.4 5G PPP collaboration activities. Within the regular WP/Task meetings, the project representatives update each other on the developments of each of the WGs and a common strategy for sharing results and insights and/or participation in 5G PPP activities and deliverables is drawn, making sure that all necessary input is provided towards 5G PPP and that VITAL-5G participates in all relevant activities.

2.2 5G PPP Steering Board (SB)

2.2.1 SB overview

The Steering Board is comprised of the PCs of the funded projects under the 5G PPP umbrella or other nominated representatives and is responsible to take common actions and initiatives to achieve the programme's objectives. The SB is a "living organism" as representatives of projects that are finished, are stepping out of the group, while members of newly awarded projects are joining. Currently the SB counts 53 active projects split over six different parts of the Phase 3 of the 5G PPP programme, as depicted in Table 3

Table 3: Currently active projects in the 5G PPP SB

Project Phase / Part	Project category	Number of projects
5G PPP Phase 3, Part 1	Infrastructure projects (ICT-17)	3
5G PPP Phase 3, Part 2	Automotive projects (ICT-18)	3
5G PPP Phase 3, Part 3	Advanced 5G validation trials across multiple vertical industries (ICT-19)	8
5G PPP Phase 3, Part 4	5G Long Term Evolution projects (ICT-20)	8
5G PPP Phase 3, Part 5	5G Core Technologies innovation and 5G for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) (ICT-42 & ICT-53)	8 (ICT-42) 4 (ICT-53)
5G PPP Phase 3, Part 6	5G innovations for verticals with third party services & Smart Connectivity beyond 5G (ICT-41 & ICT-52)	9 (ICT-41) 10 (ICT-52)

At least one member from each project has to participate in the SB's regular calls, to align among the group and to offer updates with regards to the respective project. Common actions are also agreed, such as the update of regular 5G PPP documents (e.g., the Key Achievements⁴, the 5G PPP Vision and Mission papers⁵, the TOP 20 technical documents, the Trials & Pilots Brochure [1], the Platforms Cartography⁶), white-papers and more. A chairman is nominated after elections among the members. Currently Dan Warren from Samsung is serving as SB chairman.

2.2.2 SB activities & VITAL-5G contributions

The Project Coordinator (from WINGS) and the deputy participant (from ICP) are participating in all the SB telcos and events, to synch with the other projects. Due to the pandemic, a face-to-face meeting of the SB has not taken place during the lifetime of the VITAL-5G hence all meetings have been held online (virtual).

The SB is responsible for the organizational management of the entire 5G PPP and the delegation of activities to the TB and the rest of the WGs. As such, SB participants are mostly expected to provide basic project information which are stored on the online common repository (BSCW), and to represent their projects in the various decisions that have to be made. The SB takes decisions as to how to proceed with certain subjects and then assigns the relevant action points to the WGs and potentially to respective partners. During the SB meetings, an overview is provided by the TB Chairman and each of WG Chairmen, regarding the progress achieved in the last period.

In the first eighteen months of the project, the VITAL-5G PC has participated in most of the SB meetings, and took part in all the decisions made, with the best interest of VITAL-5G at heart. As explained before, most tangible

⁴ <https://5g-ppp.eu/key-achievements-v3-1/>

⁵ <https://5g-ppp.eu/roadmaps/>

⁶ <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-platforms-cartography/>

contributions come from the TB and the WG, however, some tangible contributions were also provided by the PC towards the SB. Those are:

- Signing and provisioning the VITAL-5G Collaboration Agreement (CA)
- Presentation of the VITAL-5G in the dedicated ICT-41 Webinar organized by the SB
 - 5G PPP: 5G Innovations for verticals
- Declaration of project representatives in all the 5G PPP WGs
- Contribution of content to the 5G PPP Static Project web page content⁷
- Contribution of content to 5G PPP Phase3_2021_Projects Brochure (see **Annex I**)
- Delivery of the project Deliverables list, summarizing all the deliverables expected by every project and their due dates.
- Contribution of contents to the Trials & Pilots_Summary document (see **Annex II**)
- Coordination on the participation in EuCNC⁸ 2022 in Grenoble, France
- Approval of proposed white papers and delegation of most appropriate partner to contribute to the respective WG (White papers then handled at the WG level)
- Alignment on the next version of the projects Cartography
- Day to day admin operations on behalf of VITAL-5G

Through the participation of the PC in the SB, the contributions of VITAL-5G towards the 5G PPP are synchronized, and the dissemination of the project's results towards all relevant channels is ensured. Moreover, additional opportunities were created by the participation in the SB, as it was the birthing ground for several online workshops and most notable the application for an ICT-41 organized Workshop at the EuCNC 2022, which was accepted as a Special Session entitled "NetApps for Verticals"⁹.

2.2.3 VITAL-5G next steps within the SB

The project is going to continuously be represented at the SB level by the PC and the deputy nominee, to ensure the alignment with the other 5G PPP projects. Regular attendance and contribution to the common documents of the SB as well as towards the shaping of the next steps of the entire 5G PPP are the basic pillars of the participation in the SB. As the project will enter its more mature phase, and results from trials will start becoming available over the next period (M18-M36), the SB representatives will make sure to raise awareness about the project outcomes, present the results and insights, and discuss with other projects towards a common understanding and the generation of globally applicable guidelines. The most important targets from the project's participation in the SB over the next period are:

- Dissemination of project results and announcement of the various project dissemination activities (Webinars, Demos, hackathons, workshops) at the SB level
- Contribution to relevant white papers to disseminate the project results and share the lessons learned on relevant topics (5G performance & architecture, slicing, NetApps, KPI monitoring & analysis, etc.)
- Co-organization of workshops/events with other ICT-41 projects and/or other relevant projects working on a common aspect/technology
- Coordination of the project's contribution to all the standard 5G PPP documentation (Trials & Pilots Brochure, Golden nuggets, key Achievements, Top 20 Technical Documents, project Heritage figure)
- Participation in the upcoming physical meetings to contribute to the update of the roadmap of 5G PPP

⁷ <https://5g-ppp.eu/Vital-5G/>

⁸ <https://www.eucnc.eu/>

⁹ <https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/special-sessions/special-session-10/>

2.3 5G PPP Technology Board (TB)

2.3.1 TB overview

The 5G PPP Technology Board (TB) is constituted by the Technical Managers of all the active 5G PPP projects (around 50 members at the time of writing) and it is currently chaired by Mikael Fallgren, Ericsson. The VITAL-5G representatives are Giada Landi, NXW, (VITAL-5G Technical Manager) and Kostas Trichias, WINGS, as deputy (VITAL-5G Project Coordinator). The 5G PPP TB, in cooperation with the 5G PPP SB (see Figure 1), aims to facilitate the communications and the interactions between the projects to ensure the coherence and the effectiveness of their combined results, as well as the consistency of the technological solutions designed and developed in the single research initiatives with the objectives of the global 5G PPP programme. The 5G PPP TB meetings are organized with bi-weekly conference calls, dedicated to the day-by-day coordination and synchronization of the project activities, and periodical workshops (usually 2 workshops per year, currently in virtual mode due to the pandemic restrictions), where the projects present their scientific and technical outcomes organized in clusters per technological area.

Figure 1: Position of Technology Board in 5G PPP structure

2.3.2 TB activities & VITAL-5G contributions

The 5G PPP TB is coordinating several initiatives to disseminate the 5G PPP projects' results through consolidated reports or brochures that combines the main achievements of all the projects. VITAL-5G is actively participating to the preparation of this material, with contributions in the following areas:

- Cartographies related to involved vertical industries, 5G KPIs, 5G platforms and testbeds capabilities, and mapping of the technological areas covered by the project to the 6G topics in the NetWorld Europe Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).
- Heritage Figure, to show the interactions between projects of the various 5G PPP phases, with focus on the reuse and evolution of their technical achievements and results along the 5G PPP path from the first to the third phase.
- Survey of main documents and key achievements produced by the projects.
- Creation of a Reference Figure to show the distribution and positioning of the various projects in technological clusters.
- Survey of planned trials and pilots, as input for the future 5G Trials Roadmap.

Some contributions provided in this context have been reported in **Annex III – V**.

Moreover, the 5G PPP TB has facilitated the coordination among the ICT-41 projects (from the call on “5G innovations for verticals with third party services”) for the preparation of a joint Special Session “NetApps for Verticals”, which will be held at EuCNC 2022 and where VITAL-5G will present its results on NetApps for Transport & Logistic.

2.3.3 VITAL-5G next steps within the TB

The 5G PPP TB publishes periodically a Trials & Pilots brochure where the projects have the opportunity to report their main achievements in terms of KPIs results and experimental validation of the developed technologies in vertical-oriented trials. VITAL-5G plans to contribute to the next two editions of this brochure, relying on the experiments’ results from the first round of trials, dedicated to internal use cases, and the second round of trials, extended to third party users. Moreover, the VITAL-5G outcomes for NetApp design, modelling, development and testing will be presented in future 5G PPP TB workshops, where ICT-41 projects will organize dedicated sessions of the agenda to discuss their approaches around the NetApps topic.

2.4 5G PPP Working Groups (WGs)

This section provides details regarding the 5G PPP WGs that VITAL-5G participates in, highlighting the WGs objectives, the work carried out during the reporting period and the respective contributions from the VITAL-5G partners and the goals for the next period.

2.4.1 Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation (TMV) WG

2.4.1.1 WG overview

The Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation (TMV) Working Group was founded as part of the 5G PPP effort to promote commonalities across projects that have strong interest in the T&M methodologies needed to provide support to the vertical use cases in the 5G Trial Networks. Such efforts include the development of Test and Measurement methods, test cases, procedures and KPI formalization and validation to the greatest possible extent, ensuring a unique European vision on how to support the entire lifecycle of the 5G network, from R&D to actual deployed environments.

The Group is comprised by several Phase II and Phase III 5G PPP projects, and it considers the following research areas and technology domains:

- Testing KPI definition, KPI sources, collection procedures and analysis
- Testing frameworks (requirements, environment, scenarios, expectations, limitation) and tools
- Testing methodologies and procedures
- KPI validation methodologies
- Testing lifecycle (i.e., testing execution, monitoring, evaluation and reporting)

- Common information models for 5G T&M

Another important topic is the use of and contribution towards open-source projects such as OSM, OPNFV or ONAP and identification of relevant exploitation and dissemination targets to promote the European vision on T&M towards a more global adoption.

2.4.1.2 WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions

During the reporting period VITAL-5G represented by WINGS participated in all TMV WG biweekly telcos, in order to discuss the WG current activities, progress and identify next steps. WINGS also holds the role of the TMV WG chair via our colleague Vaggelis Kosmatos who is leading the WG activities. In addition, WINGS contributed to one whitepaper already published by the TMV WG and one ongoing whitepaper. Finally, WINGS participated to the contributions provided by TMV toward the ETSI INT and participated in the organization and presentation of a TMV WG webinar.

Whitepaper on 5G performance results

In the 5G PPP project a large number of 5G performance results are collected. The first questions that emerge from the experts and non-experts (verticals) and tried to be answered using the outcome are the following: a) are the results close to the 5G theoretical values and the KPI targets promised by the 5G domain? b) can we identify some factors that practically affects the results, while others not? c) do the results fulfil the application requirements or better, do the results satisfy the expectations of the verticals?

In this whitepaper, we tried to give answers to the first and second questions, while the third question can be answered when the results from the ICT-19 projects will become available (as a next version of the current document and in cooperation with the vertical KPI Task Force).

Therefore, in the current white paper the effort is focused on trying to clarify the details behind the performance numbers and provide a series of interpretation guidelines that could help the reader better understanding the 5G domain. In addition, based on the analysis of performance results, the main impact factors that affect the results are identified, while a high-level explanation is provided that is clearly understandable by non-experts. The motivation is to create a first bridge between the telecommunications and verticals domains and reach a common understanding in explaining what they can really expect from 5G.

The white paper is available from the 5G PPP website [1] or directly on Zenodo¹⁰.

Whitepaper on 5G KPI measurement tools

The whitepaper is entitled “KPIs Measurement Tools - From KPI definition to KPI validation” and has the below objectives:

- To provide a comprehensive presentation of the 5G KPI measurement available tools / available infrastructures / available frameworks and platforms / available data infrastructures
- To provide best practices on how to perform 5G measurements
- In the discussion chapter presents lessons learned and insights from the use of the tools

The whitepaper is ongoing with a plan to be published by end of July 2022.

Contribution to ETSI INT

TMV WG provided contributions in ETSI INT in TR about recommendation on Application Testing and Validation Frameworks (ETSI TR 103 761)

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5094973>

The purpose of this technical report is to provide recommendations on methodologies for end-to-end testing and validation of vertical applications over 5G and beyond networks. Such recommendations can be equally applicable to a wide range of industry verticals, application cases and beyond 5G scenarios.

The final document was published in ETSI [3].

Webinar

TMV WG organized a webinar on “Practical insights from 5G Test, Measurement and KPI Validation with vertical applications” in 18 June 2021 09:00 – 13:00. WINGS participated in the organization and presentation of a TMV WG webinar.

This webinar presented the results of the work group, which are two-fold. The first session focused on the presentation and contextualization of the performance results obtained so far, as well as identifying the impact factors that influence the performance. The second session focused on the mapping of verticals service and application KPIs onto network performance KPIs, as well as exemplifying this mapping for several vertical sectors.

The webinar content can be found on 5G PPP’s website here¹¹.

2.4.1.3 VITAL-5G next steps within this WG

VITAL-5G during the next period will continue its active participation in TMV WG by participating in all the TMV WG telcos and contributing the TMV WG whitepapers. VITAL-5G plans to provide further contributions to the following TMV WG related topics:

- KPI definition
- KPI collection and monitoring
- Testing frameworks (requirements, environment, scenarios, expectations, limitation) and tools
- Testing methodologies and procedures
- KPI validation methodologies

2.4.2 Vision and Societal Challenges WG

2.4.2.1 WG overview

The Vision and Societal Challenges WG has a broad remit among which, according to the 5G PPP website¹², includes identifying “... the societal, economic, environmental, business and technological benefits obtainable from the realization of 5G...”. The group also examines publicly available material to better understand the commonalities and/or differences in major technical trends across the global research community and industrial sector.

VITAL-5G is represented on the Business Validation, Models, and Ecosystems sub-group (BVME-SG), which is part of the wider Vision and Societal Challenges WG. The BVME-SG analyses the commercial opportunities that can be derived from 5G network rollout. This helps to provide a better understanding of the future potential of the 5G market for the wide variety of actors in the associated ecosystem. By analysing business-related activities across the 5G PPP projects, the BVME-SG identify key stakeholders in the ecosystem and aim to articulate the business models that could help deliver 5G-based products/services. The BVME-SG is led by Telenor, it has approximately 20 members, and meets bi-weekly.

¹¹ <https://5g-ppp.eu/event/practical-insights-from-5g-test-measurement-and-kpi-validation-with-vertical-applications/>

¹² <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-work-groups/>

2.4.2.2 *WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions*

VITAL-5G is represented in the BVME-SG by ICP, who regularly joins the BVME-SG bi-weekly meetings, particularly since October 2021. ICP are actively involved in the activities of this subgroup, specifically in relation to the development of a white paper in the area of 5G ecosystem business modelling, which is under development currently. This has involved 1) numerous discussions on potential content, 2) creating material for and reviewing an initial draft of the paper's introduction, and 3) an on-going activity to review previously submitted deliverables from other 5G PPP projects in order to understand how business-related activities were managed in each of the projects. The goal of this latter item is to gather insights that could potentially be integrated into the proposed white paper when describing best practices on business validation. VITAL-5G has also contributed to a proposal for a workshop on 5G and Beyond-5G ecosystems (more detail in Section 3.2).

2.4.2.3 *VITAL-5G next steps within this WG*

The goal for VITAL-5G's contribution to the BVME-SG in the next year is to continue to contribute to the upcoming white paper mentioned above, specifically in terms of 1) engaging in discussions on the structure and content, 2) reviewing/editing drafts, and 3) creating content based on the business modelling best practice analysis of other 5G PPP projects. ICP will also contribute to the technical committee of the IEEE Globecom 2022 workshop on "The emerging 5G and 6G ecosystems", discussed in Section 3.2.

2.4.3 **Software Network WG**

2.4.3.1 *WG overview*

The software network workgroup aims to analyse and address unification and applicability of key research topics related to Software Networking. This refers to both the uses cases in areas such as IoT and Wire or Wireless Networks as well as software defined concepts. Among the 5G related concepts one could focus on Software Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) as developed and promoted by the 5G PPP projects. The overall effort towards digitalization is not only of interest in 5G PPP but also in the ITU-T Study Group13 [Study Group 13, ITU-T,¹³], that focuses on emerging 5G technologies.

VITAL-5G is represented in the 5G PPP Software Network Group and aims to support 5G softwarization through whitepapers on topics such as data exposure via APIs and through events related to NetApps. The goal is to optimize software related processes in 5G networks, reduce their costs and bring added value to network infrastructure by making the services more flexible, accessible and easy to redesign to address user needs.

2.4.3.2 *WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions*

Whitepaper on NetApp exposure services

VITAL-5G partners contributed to the whitepaper "NetApp: Opening up 5G and beyond networks (5G-PPP projects analysis)" [4], published in 2021, which addresses aspects related to the usage of API interfaces specific to various verticals, whether the application developers should adapt to each required API interface and whether infrastructure providers should adapt for each private 5G deployment.

The main subjects are below:

- NetApps definition and API exposure refers to the software needs to interact with the control plane of a mobile network by consuming exposed APIs (e.g., Northbound APIs of 5G core and/or MEC APIs) in a standardized and trusted way to compose services for the vertical industries. The YANG data model is described and languages, such as OpenAPI are reviewed since they provide the necessary tools to

¹³ <http://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/studygroups/2013-2016/13/Pages/default.aspx>

describe the data models. For control and management, Representational State Transfer (REST) with HyperText Transfer Protocol (HTTP) is presented.

- Network API to vertical API translation focuses on the review of several projects that aim to improve the NetApp onboarding, deployment and orchestration. Improvement of testing and validation is also a topic considered. The Vital 5G testbeds and their exposed interfaces are described in this section.
- Security related methods for CAPIF are briefly reviewed.

Vital-5G Software Network Presentation in the 5GPPP SN WG

In the 5G PPP Architecture WG meeting held on the 18th of February 2022, ORO held a presentation on the VITAL-5G Project, covering aspects such as: 5G Testbeds Software Architecture, NetApps (Application –specific NetApps, Application – agnostic NetApps, NetApp implementation), Experimentation Portal, VITAL-5G Trials, 3rd party experimenters.

Vital-5G NetApps Presentation at 5GASP NetApp Launch Event

During the 5GASP NetApp Launch event (19th of May 2022), BEIA held a presentation on the VITAL-5G NetApp Ecosystem, entitled “An example of Vertical Specific NetApp: On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel”, covering the following Use case: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras.

2.4.3.3 VITAL-5G next steps within this WG

In the upcoming period, the focus will be on developing Cloud-Native architecture concepts on the project testbeds as this is mandatory in order to meet customer demands for new services. Moreover, one important next step regarding VITAL-5G’s contribution to this WG are the on-going activities for publishing an IEEE ComMA Paper based on Arch WP4.0.

2.4.4 5G Architecture WG

2.4.4.1 WG overview

The main objective of this Working Group is to ensure collaboration between 5GPPP projects on 5G/6G architectural concepts or components, while also contributing to creating a consensus on building these architectures. In detail, its objectives are:

- Research on 5G/6G architectures.
- Collect and analyse business or technical requirements in the 5G/6G era.
- Elaborate architecture solutions to meet the above-mentioned requirements.
- Study existing approaches or initiatives on interoperability between 5G/6G architectures.
- Facilitate consensus building, migration policies and elaborate roadmaps
- Support 5GPPP projects and the Pre-Standardization WG for collaboration with standardisation organizations such as 3GPP RAN, IETF, 3GPP SA2, ITU-R, ETSI, ONF, NGMN, etc.

2.4.4.2 WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions

Whitepaper on 5G Architecture [5]

The whitepaper reviews trends on novel architectural aspects and innovations from business related considerations to the related services, focusing on the service layer as a management interface and on NetApps that make use of network slicing. Network automation through control loops, usage of AI algorithms, the programmable network infrastructure and the orchestrated operation of virtual resources, all make the resources more readily available to the users through exposed APIs. The interoperation of private and public

networks is also discussed in the context of various use cases such as eMBB and high-speed mobility for transportation, immersive media and VR, smart energy metering, remote training, etc.

VITAL-5G partners contributed to this white paper with content addressing the whole VNF lifecycle and optimization of the deployment and instantiation, orchestration and monitoring of services, as well as improvement of virtualized infrastructures, SDNs, VIM, slices and resource orchestrators. The importance of KPIs is also noted in terms of availability and redundancy of coverage, guaranteed QoS for latency, jitter, throughput, ease of customization, E2E control management, data protection, integration of cloud, power saving and dynamic network control.

ML usage for self-configuration, self-optimization and self-healing is discussed and the importance of a cloud native approach for resource and workload orchestration is highlighted. Whether for the core or the various types of edge architectures (regional, access, enterprise, device), a service-based architecture with dedicated network functions is necessary. Further, it is noted that the resilient transport network and backhaul integration need to be given due consideration.

Vital-5G Architecture Presentation in 5G PPP Architecture WG

In the 5G PPP Architecture WG meeting held on the 23rd of June 2021, ORO held a presentation on the VITAL-5G Project, covering aspects such as: Project Concept 5G Testbeds Architecture (CI/CD Framework, Management/Orchestration, NFV/VNFs, Microservices, 5G Testing Area, 5G RRUs, 5G RAN, 5G PMR, 5G Core), T&L facilities & 5G-enabled use cases, Project Timeline.

Vital-5G Architecture Presentation at 5GASP NetApp Launch Event

As part of our 5GPPP collaboration, during the 5GASP NetApp Launch Event (19th of May 2022), ORO held a presentation of the 5G Testbed of the VITAL-5G Project, where the main focus was on elaborating the key points of the 5G architecture and the current status of its implementation. The presentation covered the checked milestones and implemented modules such as: elaborated software design and an early subset of components and basic functionalities (NetApp package and VSB management, NetApp blueprint validation, Vertical Service provisioning, Experiment management).

2.4.4.3 VITAL-5G next steps within this WG

The VITAL-5G's efforts will be focused on bringing technology into practice for the Use Cases described, while also providing enhanced KPIs and enabling the first trials of 5G powered NetApps for Transport & Logistics verticals. Results from this work will be reported to the 5G Architecture WG.

2.4.5 5G Security WG

2.4.5.1 WG overview

The 5G PPP Security Work Group launched in 2016 as an initiative from the 5G-ENSURE project with the scope of discussing 5G Security topics related to architecture and vision in this field. The WG was initially present in 5G IA but since 2017 has been available also to 6G-IA members. The principal scope of this WG is to enable the development of a 5G Security Community, made of both experts and practitioners that share information and discuss security topics or trends in order to align and fasten progress on topics of the 5G / 6G Security field. This scope is to be achieved through the use of new technologies such as communications / events / whitepapers / workshops and also through interaction with other WGs.

2.4.5.2 WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions

Although security aspects of 5G infrastructures have not been directly addressed by VITAL-5G within the 5G Security WG, some security aspects such as Authentication (CAPIF_Security / AEF_Security_API), Authorization (CAPIF_Security / AEF_Security_API), Access control policy (CAPIF_Access_Control_Policy), On/off boarding

(CAPIF_API_invoker_management) have been covered in the Software Network WG whitepaper [4] under the section → CAPIF Services → Security services. Efforts from the VITAL-5G consortium so far were focused on following the 5GPPP Security Work Group activities.

2.4.5.3 WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions

So far there have not been any specific T&L topics or use cases covered by the 5GPPP Security WG. We do intend to cover the security aspects of 5G architectures, where necessary, as part of our contribution in the Software Network WG, 5G Architecture WG or 5G Security WG. In the meantime, project partners keep monitoring the 5GPPP Security WG activities through participation in the WG meetings and elaborating on the security related technical trends covered by this body.

2.4.6 Trials WG

2.4.6.1 WG overview

The Trials Working Group was launched by 5G Infrastructure Association in September 2016 after the publication of the 5G Manifesto of industry in Europe [6] and in the context of the 5G Action Plan of the EU Commission [7]. According to the 5G Manifesto, industry in Europe will develop by the beginning of 2017 a European trial roadmap on technology trials and Pan-European trials with vertical sector use cases.

The objectives of the Working Group are:

- To develop the European Trial Roadmap based on the 5G Manifesto.
- To facilitate the involvement of verticals in the trials roadmap.
- To discuss and define business principles underpinning the economic viability of trials.
- To consider and coordinate the activity on trials with other relevant initiatives at international level.
- To investigate and propose how to link trials to Horizon 2020 5G PPP Phase 3 in order to get funding for parts of the overall trial roadmap.

The Trials WG meets periodically, usually once every ~3 months.

2.4.6.2 WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions

Since the beginning of VITAL-5G, representatives of the consortium members have participated actively in the WG meetings and have provided the following contributions:

- Presentation of the VITAL-5G projects and pilots, emphasizing the Romanian use case (river port).
- Contribution to the online verticals' cartography and assessment of all the pilots and trials etc in 5G PPP within the FULL5G CSA project, as depicted in Figure 2.
- As participants in VITAL-5G and leaders of Use Case (UC) 2 (Smart Port/Smart River in Romania, Galați), BEIA has volunteered as rapporteur for Romania in the Smart city trials in Europe report elaborated in the Trials WG by describing the UC and associated information.

Figure 2: VITAL-5G input to verticals tracker

2.4.6.3 VITAL-5G next steps within this WG

The partners involved in the WG are monitoring for any contribution opportunity within the WG. For now, contributions to the ongoing White Paper: *Verticals towards 6G: challenges and opportunities*, are envisioned. As part of this WG, VITAL-5G partners plan to contribute insights based on Trials experience in VITAL-5G project (sea and river ports - Transport & Logistics vertical). Moreover, a contribution to the next edition (estimated autumn 2022) of EC H2020 5G Infrastructure PPP - PPP T&Ps Brochure [1] is planned. The Trials WG regularly releases a trials and pilots brochure (currently at no. 4) to be disseminated by 6G-IA. When VITAL-5G will have preliminary results, we are committed to contributing and presenting them in the WG.

2.4.7 5G for Connected and Automated Mobility (5G4CAM) WG

2.4.7.1 WG overview

The 5G4CAM WG is established as a means of supporting 5G for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) activities funded under EU Programmes covering both R&I and deployment activities in two work streams:

1. **R&I**: the WG aims at becoming a knowledge base to facilitate the exchange of information on ongoing R&I activities in the field and to disseminate it, e.g., in the form of white papers. The WG also aims at developing suggestions for Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas for Smart Networks and Services (SNS) Joint Undertaking and the new European PPP on Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM).
2. **Deployment**: the WG aims at developing elements of strategic guidance in view of European deployment programmes in the field, in particular 5G Corridors for CAM under the CEF2 Digital Programme. The group also aims at facilitating broader stakeholder cooperation and building of project pipelines through workshops and networking activities.

The 5G4CAM WG now operates under the 6G-Industry Association (6G-IA) framework with a broader scope of encompassing Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G technologies to promote the advancement of CAM and to foster the deployment of relevant infrastructure.

2.4.7.2 WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions

Two VITAL-5G partners (WINGS and BEIA) participate in the regular WG activities including weekly telcos, workshops and webinar organization. The WG is separated in two different streams, as described above, which are addressed interchangeably. As VITAL-5G partners also have experience from previous CAM projects (ICT-18, ICT-52) they also assist in the discussions regarding the transition from research results and trials/pilots towards real-life deployments and implementation. The participating VITAL-5G partners contributed to the following activities of the WG, during this reporting period:

- **Project presentation**: Upon joining the activities of the WG the project representatives presented the project's objectives and goals and discussed the role of autonomous mobility within VITAL-5G.
- **Discussions on the ICT-18 deployment study**: VITAL-5G partners were updated on the insights of the deployment study produced by the ICT-18 projects and engaged in the resulting discussions regarding the deployment gaps and the role that B5G and 6G technologies could play in that regard.
- **White paper**: the above discussions led to a white paper entitled "*From 5G to 6G Vision - A Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) perspective*" in which the VITAL-5G partners played a key role. The project's Coordinator (Kostas Trichias) took on the role of one of the co-editors, while the project partners also made contributions with regards to the identified gaps from the perspective of the T&L sector and the expectation from 6G technologies. The paper is targeted to be published during the week of EuCNC 2022.
- **Events preparation**: As part of the weekly agenda, the WG's projects participation in major events were discussed and co-organized. Participation in events such as the European Conference on Networks and Communication & 6G Summit (EuCNC¹⁴ & 6G Summit) and the ITS European Congress¹⁵ were discussed among project participants and common actions were agreed.
- **Active discussions and webinars**: As part of the weekly agenda the WG's members engaged in various discussions on important issues about the future of CAM and the various European initiatives that support it. As such the members were informed about the publication of important documents such as the CCAM SRIA¹⁶, and the CEF2 call preparation, while liaisons with other important initiatives such as the Connected Motorcycle Consortium¹⁷ (CMC) also took place and strengthened the common vision towards the evolution of CAM. Figure 3 presents the CMC roadmap as presented to the WG which verifies the commonalities with the CAM roadmap discussed in the WG.

¹⁴ <https://www.eucnc.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://itseuropeancongress.com/>

¹⁶ https://www.ccam.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/CCAM_SRIA-report_web.pdf

¹⁷ <https://www.cmc-info.net/>

Figure 3: CMC roadmap as presented and discussed at the 5G4CAM WG

2.4.7.3 VITAL-5G next steps within this WG

VITAL-5G partners have a strong commitment with this WG and will continue to actively participate in all its activities. Besides the finalization of the ongoing white paper, the VITAL-5G partners have committed to share trials results and insights as soon as they become available, in order to further discuss the role of 5G enabled CAM in the T&L sector and which technologies are expected to play a significant role. Moreover, project partners will engage in comparative studies with other project results and will actively contribute towards the dissemination of the WG’s outcome via additional white papers and workshops/webinars.

2.4.8 5G-PPP SME WG

2.4.8.1 WG overview

The 5G-PPP working group originated from NetworldEurope and is currently chaired by Mr. Jacques Magen. Its main objectives are:

- Help and support SMEs participation in the SNS Partnership and more generally in EU R&D projects.
- Improve visibility of SMEs in the SNS ecosystem and in general in EU R&D programmes, and ease/promote participation in NetworldEurope. Activate channels that may enable, facilitate and promote SME contribution into the NetworldEurope SRIA and research topics, and SME involvement through other strategic documents related to NetworldEurope and to SNS (e.g., SNS work programmes).
- Ensure that the interests of SMEs, a key player in the EU economy, are adequately taken into account, more particularly in NetworldEurope and in SNS.
- Act as representative/interlocutor of SMEs in the telecom domain, more particularly in NetworldEurope and in SNS.
- Help SMEs access European funds, in SNS and beyond. The WG could e.g., “pre-digest” material and help SMEs find their way into SNS-related funding and beyond.

- Analyse the participation of SMEs in projects, potentially prepare questionnaire and transmit the conclusions and results to European Commission, for SNS in particular.

The SME WG also has a strong link to the 6G Infrastructure Association¹⁸, with one of its representatives in the Board of the Association.

2.4.8.2 WG activities & VITAL-5G contributions

Since its inception, SME Working Group activities have been mostly focusing on promoting the skills and expertise of SMEs in the telecommunications domain, especially towards larger companies and research organisations, and on supporting the engagement of SMEs in collaborative projects and cooperation with those players, via networking and exchange of information amongst SME representatives.

The main activities of the SME WG include:

- Quarterly telephone conferences + ad-hoc telcos whenever required;
- Regular updates of the “Find your SME” web page¹⁹, including the SME brochure²⁰ and the SME success stories²¹;
- Interaction amongst SMEs;
- Participation in events e.g., with dedicated SME-related presentations;

Other SME promotional activities e.g., report to NetworkWorldEurope Steering Board and the 5G Initiative Steering Board meetings. VITAL-5G contributes in these activities through the participation of its members to the calls and presentations when the opportunity arises. The VITAL-5G consortium members that participate take part in the discussions in order to promote the project and follow up on important topics that concern 5G-PPP.

2.4.8.3 VITAL-5G next steps within this WG

As the VITAL-5G project continues, the respective delegates from the project will be participating in all of the SME WG meetings and activities trying to contribute to all white papers produced by the WG as well as join any collaborations that fit the mission of the project and can boost its presence.

¹⁸ <https://6g-ia.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://www.networld europe.eu/find-the-sme-you-need-new-page/>

²⁰ <https://bscw.5g-ppp.eu/pub/bscw.cgi/d437286/2021-07%20SME%20Brochure.pdf>

²¹ https://www.networld europe.eu/find-the-sme-you-need-new-page/#SUCCESS_STORIES

3 Collaboration Outcomes

3.1 White Papers

As described in the previous sections, the VITAL-5G partners have been actively contributing to various activities of the 5G PPP WGs that are relevant with the project work. Perhaps some of the most tangible results of the work that the various WGs perform, are the published White Papers, which accumulate the knowledge of the various projects and share their results, insights and considered ways forward. As the VITAL-5G project matures and more knowledge is generated, the various partners contribute to such white papers from various positions. Table 4 below provides an overview of the 5G PPP white papers with VITAL-5G contributions, during this reporting period.

Table 4: VITAL-5G contributions in 5G PPP white papers

White paper	5G PPP WG	Status	VITAL-5G contributors	VITAL-5G contributions
View on 5G Architecture	Architecture WG	Published [5] (Oct. 2021)	ORO, NXW	Service Layer and NetApps Management & Orchestration
Understanding the Numbers: Contextualization and Impact Factors of 5G Performance Results	TMV WG	Published [2] (July 2021)	WINGS	White paper editors context from trial measurements
NetApp: Opening up 5G and beyond networks	Software Network WG	Ongoing	ORO	NetApps Relevant standards
KPIs Measurement Tools - From KPI definition to KPI validation	TMV WG	Ongoing	WINGS	White paper editors Testing & validation methodology
Verticals towards 6G: challenges and opportunities	Trials WG	Ongoing	BEIA	Challenges and opportunities for the T&L sector
From 5G to 6G Vision - A Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) perspective	5G4CAM WG	Published [10] June 2022	WINGS, BEIA	Co-editors, outlook on new technologies for CAM (Transport / logistics)
Innovation Trends in I4.0 enabled by 5G and Beyond Networks	5G PPP TB	Ongoing	NXW, DIA	Warehouse logistics enablers
5G Business Models	Vision and Societal Challenges WG (BVME-SG)	Ongoing	ICP	White paper contributor on business models in 5G ecosystem

3.2 Workshops

VITAL-5G participated in the preparation of a workshop proposal for EUCNC 2022, called “The emerging 5G and 6G ecosystems” as part of their activities in the BVME-SG (see Section 2.4.2). The main contribution was editing and adding content to support the writing of the proposal’s motivation section. Also, VITAL-5G was represented on the technical committee for the workshop. This proposal was not accepted by EUCNC and was resubmitted

to IEEE Globecom 2022 (4–8 December 2022, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [Hybrid]) by the BVME-SG, where it was accepted. The link to the workshop information can be found online on the event's page²².

The project has been represented in the two 5G PPP TB workshops held in remote mode on 21st May 2021 (open to all 5G PPP members) and on 18th – 19th January 2022, with an active participation on the discussions related to the design of APIs for experimentation platforms in 5G infrastructures and the sharing of common experiences and lessons learnt from pilots and pilots with 5G verticals. The exchange of ideas in these areas, especially with ICT-17 and ICT-19 projects, has been particularly useful for the refinement of some features offered by the VITAL-5G platform towards verticals and third-party developers. Moreover, the design of experimentation procedures and interfaces have been slightly adjusted considering the experiences of other 5G PPP projects, with the intention of simplifying a potential interoperability with other facilities and platform elements developed in other research initiatives.

3.3 VITAL-5G collaboration with other T&L projects

As part of the WP6 outreach activities, VITAL-5G has initiated a number of synergies with other T&L Horizon 2020 projects that are covering different aspects of the T&L sector. More specifically, the first synergy is with the Progress towards Federated Logistics through the Integration of TEN-T into A Global Trade Network (PLANET) project²³. PLANET aims to address the challenge of assessing the impact of emerging global trade corridors on the TEN-T network and ensuring effective integration of the European to the Global Network. Figure 4, depicts the approach of PLANET that goes beyond strategic transport studies and ICT for transport research, by efficiently interconnecting infrastructure (TEN-T, Rail-Freight Corridors) with geopolitical developments (e.g., future New Silk Road and emerging trade routes) and rigorously demonstrating the emerging concepts (Physical Internet) as well as technologies (IoT, Blockchain) in three EU-global real-world corridors (China – EU- US). The synergy with PLANET will include transfer of knowledge through the organization of joint workshops.

²² <https://globecom2022.ieee-globecom.org/workshop/ws23-emerging-5g-and-6g-ecosystems>

²³ <https://www.planetproject.eu/>

Figure 4: PLANET project vision to make European T&L smart, green and integrated

The second synergy is with DataPorts – Data Platform for the Cognitive Ports of the Future project²⁴. DataPorts will provide a data platform in which transportation and logistics companies around a seaport will be able to manage data like any other company asset, in order to create the basis to offer cognitive services. This will enable the connection of different digital infrastructures that are currently existing in seaports and interconnect all the seaport systems into a tightly integrated digital ecosystem. Additionally, DataPorts will create policies for a trusted and reliable data sharing and trading based on data owners’ rules and offering a clear value proposition. Finally, to leverage on the data collected to provide advanced Data Analytic services based on which the different actors in the port value chain could develop novel AI and cognitive applications.

The synergy with DataPorts launched with a common workshop between four T&L-related Horizon 2020 projects entitled “Research, as a driving force for the Maritime Transformation” (see Figure 5). In this workshop DataPorts, VITAL-5G, VesselAI²⁵ and CYRENE²⁶ projects presented their objectives and how they can collaborate by sharing data, giving access to different kind of assets (i.e., access to the installed sensors at the ports of the VITAL-5G use cases). VesselAI is building a holistic, beyond the state-of-the-art AI-empowered framework for decision-support models, data analytics and visualisations to build digital twins and maritime applications for a diverse set of cases with high impact, including simulating and predicting vessel behaviour and manoeuvring (including the human factor), ship energy design optimisation, autonomous shipping and fleet intelligence. CYRENE aims to enhance the security, privacy, resilience, accountability and trustworthiness of supply chains through the provision of a novel and dynamic Conformity Assessment Process that evaluates the security and resilience of supply chain services, the interconnected IT infrastructures composing these services and the individual devices involved in the different supply chains.

²⁴ <https://dataports-project.eu/>

²⁵ <https://vessel-ai.eu/index.html>

²⁶ <https://www.cyrene.eu/>

Figure 5: The visual of the joint workshop between DataPorts, VITAL-5G, VesselAI and CYRENE

4 Conclusions

This deliverable provided information regarding the VITAL-5G participation and contributions in 5G PPP activities and its various Working Groups. For the first half of its existence (M1-M18) the VITAL-5G partners have successfully onboarded and integrated themselves in all the key bodies and WGs of the 5G PPP and regularly attend the recurring calls and contribute to the various activities.

The high-level overview of the VITAL-5G participation was provided identifying the specific partners that contribute to each of the 5G PPP bodies. Besides the participation in the Steering Board and Technology Board which is mandated by the GA, the VITAL-5G partners participate and contribute in eight (8) 5G PPP WGs which address subjects relevant to the project's scope and goals. A detailed account of the each of these WGs scope, and activities was provided along with the specific contributions of the VITAL-5G partners in each WG for this reporting period (M1-M18).

The participation and contributions of the VITAL-5G partners in the various bodies and WGs of the 5G PPP, resulted in some tangible outcomes for this reporting period which are summarized below:

- Contributions (and co-editing for some) to 8 5G PPP White papers
- Organization of one workshop and participation to multiple others, engaging with other ICT-41 projects
- Co-organization of a special session at EuCNC 2022
- Organization of 2 webinars to disseminate key project outcomes to the 5G PPP members and beyond
- Collaboration with other projects and initiatives from the T&L ecosystem (PLANET, DataPorts, ALICE, Found.ation, VesselAI and CYRENE) [8][9].

The VITAL-5G partners have a strong commitment towards continuing and even strengthening their participation in the 5G PPP bodies and WGs, especially as the project matures and more and more results will be available to be shared with the experts of 5G PPP to engage in technical discussions. To that end, an initial draft of the consortium's plans for the continuous participation in the 5G PPP activities has been offered in this deliverable as well.

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Annex I: 5G PPP Phase 3_2021_Projects Brochure_VITAL-5G

VITAL-5G	
Project Acronym	VITAL-5G
Project Full Title	Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities
Coordinator: name, company	Kostas Trichias, WINGS ICT Solutions
Start Date – End Date	Jan 2021 - Jan 2023
Website	https://www.vital5g.eu/
e- mail	Vital-5G-Contact@5g-ppp.eu
Twitter account	@5gVital
Main Objectives & Challenges <i>(max 1000 characters spaces included)</i>	
<p>Vital-5G enables creation of 5G-enhanced services for the Transport & Logistics (T&L) industry through an open, secure and virtualised 5G test environment, designed to validate advanced T&L-related Network Applications (NetApps). Vital-5G will engage key logistics stakeholders (sea and river port authorities, road logistics operators, warehouse/hub operators) and innovative SMEs, offering them a unique opportunity to develop T&L-related services that utilise advanced 5G testbeds and vertical-specific infrastructure, otherwise unavailable to them. NetApps represent a key enabler for the adoption of 5G solutions, as they abstract the complexity of underlying 5G infrastructure for T&L application developers, and significantly reduce service creation and deployment times, while optimising 5G resource utilisation. With this approach, VITAL-5G plans to overcome the adoption barriers of 5G-based solutions in the European T&L sector and showcase the related added-value of 5G connectivity.</p>	
Applications & Expected impact <i>(max 1000 characters spaces included)</i>	
<p>VITAL-5G aims to minimize the knowledge/expertise gap between telecom providers, vertical industries and application developers through promotion and validation of Network Applications (NetApps). The targeted 5G-enhanced T&L applications are expected to have the following impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i)Faster adoption of 5G-based solutions in the T&L ecosystem based on innovative NetApps, validated through a flexible 5G virtualized environment. ii)Enhanced service creation time and lifecycle management of 5G-enabled T&L services through mechanisms to transparently design, onboard, and manage NetApps across multiple domains and 5G networks. iii)Wider-scale T&L vertical impact through gathering validated NetApps in an open-source repository, for leverage by 3rd party developers. iv)Considerable commercialisation potential from novel 5G technologies and services, the implementation and validation of which can support creation of new SME-driven commercial products and service for the T&L market and beyond. 	
Vertical use cases addressed	Please tick the relevant ones
Industry 4.0	
Agriculture & Agri-Food	
Automotive	
Transport & Logistics	x
Smart Cities & utilities	
Public Safety	
Smart airports	
Energy	
ehealth & wellness	
Media & entertain	

Figure 6: VITAL-5G contribution to the 5G PPP SB Project Brochure

Annex II: 5G PPP Trials & Pilots Summary Document – VITAL-5G

Table 5: VITAL-5G contribution to the 5G PPP Trial & Pilots Summary Document

Phase 3 Projects ICT-41	Trials & Pilots Names /UCs	Trials & Pilots Verticals Sectors	Trials & Pilots Locations	Trials & Pilots Dates
VITAL-5G	Automated Vessel Transport	Transport & Logistics	Port of Antwerp	2022 - 2023
	5G Connectivity and Data-enabled Assisted Navigation using IoT Sensing and Video Cameras	Transport & Logistics	Galati Danube river port	2022 – 2023
	Automation & Remote Operation of Freight Logistics (Warehouse Logistics)	Transport & Logistics	Athens	2022 - 2023

Annex III: 5G PPP Projects Heritage – VITAL-5G

Table 6: VITAL-5G contribution to the 5G PPP Heritage picture

Phase 3 Projects ICT-41	Phase 2 / 1 Projects / Phase 3 Projects	Components Use / Re-use
VITAL-5G	5G-EVE	Upgrade OTE’s and NSA’s 5G testbed to support 3GPP R.16 SA. Reuse 5G-EVE Portal dashboard, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager and the Experiment Execution Manager as a base for VITAL-5G Service Portal and extend it to support NetApps and intelligent VxF placement. Customise the Experiment Execution Manager to support T&L validation process.
	5G-SOLUTIONS	Extend the functionality of the KPI visualization system to cover the GUI of the VITAL-5G Open Platform and additional KPIs. Reuse of Customer, discovery templates for value assessment in T&L operational roadmaps for Financial, People, Product, Marketing and Sales. Reuse of innovative IPR.
	5G-EVE, 5G-MOBIX, 5G-TOURS, 5G-HEART, CLEAR-5G	Extend the functionality of the WINGS big data analytics platform to accommodate the unique semantics of logistics environments and to control/cooperate with AGVs and warehouse automation. Update robotics/AGV autonomous functionality.
	5G-EVE, 5G-MEDIA, 5G-CITY	Transform Nextworks’ 5G-catalogue to implement the core engine of the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository for NetApps. Implement the new functionalities for selective onboarding of NetApps and VxF/VNF in NFV infrastructures and MANO and integrate eLicensing mechanisms to manage license schemes.
	MATILDA	Extend microservice based capabilities to allow for the implementation of the appropriate fusion techniques and the development of advanced AI mechanisms for the optimization of logistic & inspection operations.
	5G-CARMEN	Reuse CCAM platform that provides a two-tiered orchestration capability for vertical, vertical-agnostic, and 5G network applications. The platform can provide the means for orchestrating various NetApps in diversified domains; Life Cycle Management operations performed by two-tier SDN & NFV MANO orchestrators can be customized to specific NetApps.

Annex IV: 5G PPP Platform Cartography - KPIs Cartography – VITAL-5G

Table 7: VITAL-5G contribution to the 5G PPP KPIs cartography

Platforms KPIs	VITAL-5G
User Data Rate	Target values Antwerp: 500 Mbps Galati: 1 Gbps Athens: 90 Mbps Performance measurements still TBD.
Peak Data Rate	Target values Antwerp: 800 Mbps Galati: 200 Mbps in UL Athens: 200 Mbps Performance measurements still TBD.
Capacity	Target values Antwerp: 1.8 Mbps/m ² Galati: 10 Mbps/m ² Athens: 10 Mbps/m ² Performance measurements still TBD.
Latency	Target values Antwerp: 20 ms Galati: 3 ms Athens: 10 ms Performance measurements still TBD.
Device Density	Target values Antwerp: 300 dev/km ² Galati: 1000 dev/km ² Athens: 1000 dev/km ² Performance measurements still TBD.
Mobility	Target values Antwerp: 140 km/h Galati: 100 km/h Athens: 130 km/h Performance measurements still TBD.
Reliability	Target values Antwerp: 99.9990% Galati: > 99.99% Athens: 99,99990% Performance measurements still TBD.
Availability	Target values Antwerp: 99.9990% Galati: > 99.99% Athens: 99,99990% Performance measurements still TBD.
Position Accuracy (Location)	N/A

Service Deployment Time	Target value not defined. Performance measurements still TBD.
Energy Efficiency	N/A
Network management CAPEX/OPEX	N/A

Table 8: VITAL-5G contribution to the 5G PPP Platform Cartography

Platforms Capabilities	VITAL-5G
Rel15-5G NR in Non Standalone Alone (NSA) mode	Yes, in all VITAL-5G testbeds in Antwerp Port, Galati Port and Athens there is an intermediary phase with 5G NSA.
Rel15-5G NR with Rel15-5G Core in Standalone Alone (SA) mode ⁽⁴⁾	Yes, in all VITAL-5G testbeds.
Rel16-5G NR and 5G Core (NSA or SA) ⁽⁴⁾	Yes, in all VITAL-5G testbeds, H2-2022.
Network Slicing as a service ⁽³⁾	Partially. Network slices can be manually created and configured in all VITAL-5G testbeds in Antwerp Port, Galati Port and Athens. Programmable and on-demand slice configuration will be supported in later releases.
Customized network slice (e.g. SFC, security, enhanced Cloud access) ⁽³⁾	N/A for the moment.
Hosting of 3rd party VNFs⁽³⁾	Yes, in VITAL-5G testbeds in Antwerp Port, Galati Port and Athens.
Interworking ⁽²⁾ with other ICT17 facilities ⁽³⁾	Two VITAL-5G testbeds can be considered as evolution or extensions of 5G EVE testbeds (Athens and Galati).
Integration of additional gNB to ICT-17 facility ⁽³⁾	N/A
Edge Computing	Edge computing implemented in all VITAL-5G testbeds.
Distributed Data fabric service for analytics	Provided by VITAL-5G platform in centralized manner.
3.5 GHz 5G Radio	N78 spectrum available, low bands also possible (700MHz).
26 GHz 5G Radio	N/A
Millimetre wave for Backhaul	N/A
End User Testing	End-users will be involved in the VITAL-5G trials in the two following ways, 1) members of the consortium (T&L stakeholders and NetApps developers) will participate in the main trials and 2) 3rd party experimenters (external to the consortium) will participate in dedicated trials.

Automatic testing framework	Yes, provided by VITAL-5G platform across VITAL-5G testbeds in Antwerp Port, Galati Port and Athens.
THz Channel Testing	
AI in the Edge	
Additional Features/Capabilities	E2E network orchestration (RAN/Core/Transport).

Annex V: 5G PPP Vertical Cartography Analysis – VITAL-5G

Table 9: VITAL-5G contribution to the 5G PPP Vertical Cartography Analysis

Trial(s) / Pilot(s) Vertical UC(s) Name(s)	Brief UC Description(s): link	Vertical Cluster Vertical Category (Phase 3(.4) PSM)	Experiment Location	Type of Experiment	Estimated Experiment Date	5G ITU Functionality (eMBB / URLLC / mMTC)	Priority KPIs (prg. Level)	Vertical Consortium Partners involved
VITAL 5G: Automated Vessel Transport	This UC will showcase the automation of vessel-based logistics transport leveraging the 5G communications technology deployed in a smart port context. The vessel is outfitted with 5G connectivity to support full HD camera videos, real-time sensor data delivered to the command center, and real-time receiving of steering commands. The UC will build up a real-time digital twin around the vessel to support remotely controlled (and later on autonomous) vessels. In parallel, the UC will integrate AI/ML-based real-time route planning to optimize the port operations and to avoid idle times.	(8) Transport and Logistics	Port of Antwerp	(4) Trial	Q3 2022 - 2023	eMBB URLLC	Latency Broadband Connectivity (peak demand) Capacity (Mbps/m2)	Seafar NV, Telenet (Digitrans and IMEC as Technology providers)
VITAL 5G: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras	This UC will showcase a data-enabled assisted navigation application using IoT sensing system and video cameras installed in Galati port and on ships and barges (cargos). The objective is to permit a safer port operation and guarantee more security regarding ships navigation with the help of assisted operation / navigation even in severe weather and water conditions. In detail, the UC will demonstrate how the adoption of 5G technologies will help (i) to reduce the number of dangerous navigation events through the processing of IoT and sensors data and video streaming and (ii) to	(8) Transport and Logistics	Galati Danube river port	(4) Trial	Q3 2022 - 2023	eMBB URLLC	Latency Reliability Availability Required sustainable date rate	NAVROM, ASOCIATIA TEHNOPOL GALATI Orange Romania BEIA Consult International (as Technology provider)

	reduce the logistic costs relying on on-board monitoring and diagnosis and limiting the impact of human factor for potentially wrong decisions. Moreover, the UC will demonstrate the creation of more accurate navigation maps exploiting distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing.							
VITAL 5G: Automation and Remote Operation of Freight Logistics	This UC will demonstrate the optimization of warehousing operations through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), enabled by 5G technologies deployed in warehouse premises to support logistic services. In particular, the UC will showcase (i) the automation of AGVs operations, remotely assisted through HD video streaming to facilitate the human interaction, and (ii) the adoption of AI/ML techniques for post-processing operational data to improve the end-to-end functionality of the warehouse ecosystem.	(8) Transport and Logistics	Athens	(4) Trial	Q3 2022 - 2023	eMBB URLLC mMTC	Latency Reliability Availability	Diakinesis OTE WINGS, Incelligent (as Technology providers)

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